

Phenolic Constituents of *Ficus krishnae*

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Manuscript received 6 March 1995, accepted 15 March 1995

The plants of genus *Ficus* have been reported to possess considerable medicinal values¹ and are the rich source of coumarins². In continuation of our earlier work³ on the phytochemical investigations of *Ficus krishnae*, we now report the isolation and characterisation of a 8,8'-coumarin dimer, orlandin⁴ (1) alongwith the resacetophenone-4-methyl ether, peonol⁵ and resacetophenone-2-methyl ether, isopeonol⁶.

The air-dried leaves of *F. krishnae* (1 kg) (collected from A.M.U. Botanical Garden, Aligarh) were extracted with ethanol. The ethanol extract was concentrated to a syrupy mass under reduced pressure. The residue was treated with petrol and benzene respectively. Since the two extracts showed the similar behaviour on tlc examination, they were mixed together and chromatographed over Si-gel column. The column was eluted successively with petrol, petrol-benzene, benzene, benzene-chloroform (9 : 1-1 : 1). The eluant obtained from benzene-chloroform afforded the compounds 1, 2 and 3.

(1)

Compound-1 (50 mg) was crystallised from chloroform-ethanol as colourless crystals, m.p. 284-6°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 100-3 000 (OH), 1 680 (C=O), 1 590, 1 460 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 315, 320 nm; ^1H nmr δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.52 (6H, s, 2 \times CH₃), 3.98 (6H, s, 2 \times OCH₃), 6.66 (2H, s, H-6,6'), 6.05 (2H, s, H-3,3'); m/z M^+ 410. It was characterised as 8,8'-coumarin dimer, orlandin (1) by comparison of spectral data with the authentic sample⁴.

Compound-2 (30 mg) was crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH as needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 51°; gave a reddish violet colour with alcoholic FeCl₃; ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 990 (chelated OH), 1 670 (C=O), 1 460 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 255 nm; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 2.55 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.86 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.86 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-3), 6.90-6.94 (1H, dd, J 2.5, 8.8 Hz, H-5), 7.56 (1H, d, J 8.8 Hz, H-6), 13.5 (1H, s, chelated OH); m/z M^+ 166. Its physical data was in complete agreement with resacetophenone-4-methyl ether (peonol) and also compared with authentic sample⁵.

Compound-3 (40 mg) was crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH as colourless needles, m.p. 137-38°; gave green colour with alcoholic FeCl₃; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 200 (OH), 1 680 (C=O), 1 465 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 250 nm; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 2.56 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.84 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-3), 6.89-6.93 (1H, dd, J 2.5, 8.8 Hz, H-5), 7.54 (1H, d, J 8.8 Hz, H-6); m/z M^+ 166. It was identified as resacetophenone-2-methyl ether (isopeonol) by comparison with authentic sample⁶.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to M. R. Parthasarathy, Delhi University, New Delhi, for some useful suggestions. One of the authors (M.P.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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